

Baubinus primulae, comb. nov. (*Microbotryaceae*)

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Abstract. A new combination of *Ustilago primulae* on *Primula clusiana* in *Baubinus* is proposed.

Key words: *Baubinus*, *Microbotryum*, *Primula*, *Primulaceae*, smut fungi

Denchev *et al.* (2006) reduced the genus *Microbotryum* to include only anthericolous species (incl. *M. majus* (J. Schröt.) G. Deml & Oberw. and *M. savilei* Denchev) on *Caryophyllaceae*; *Haradaea*, a new genus, was described to accommodate the seed-destroying species of *Ustilago* on *Caryophyllaceae*. Sixty-one species formerly in *Ustilago* have been transferred into *Baubinus* (cfr Denchev *et al.* 2006).

Ustilago primulae is known only from the type description and there is no type specimen saved in any herbarium (Vánky 1998; Zwetko & Blanz 2004). Surely, this species is not a member of *Ustilago*, which species attack only plants of *Poaceae*. As *U. primulae* is similar in its symptoms and morphology to species of *Baubinus*, we propose its transferal to this genus.

Baubinus primulae (Wettst.) Denchev & R.T. Moore, *comb. nov.*

Basionym: *Ustilago primulae* Wettst., Oesterr. Bot. Z. **36**: 73, 1886.

Syn.: *Microbotryum primulae* (Wettst.) Vánky, Mycotaxon **91**: 260, 2005.

Type: on *Primula clusiana* Tausch, Austria, Nieder-Österreich, Mt Schneeberg near Vienna, 1884, J. Schneider.

References

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